

Trace Metal Elements and COVID-19 Risk Reduction

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Some counties in Iran were involved in the fourth COVID-19 infection wave intensely-quickly. Some other counties were heavily involved in the fifth wave. However, some counties (perhaps less than 50 numbers) showed relatively good resistance to both the fourth and fifth waves of the virus epidemics and became less involved. Looking at the map of counties in the fourth and fifth waves, we find that the counties that were less involved were typically concentrated in a specific geographical areas: that is, for example, two or three counties in an area, have shown infection-fire resistance. This effect of geography on COVID-19 risk can be interpreted differently and one of the possibilities is the effect of water-air-soil on reducing or increasing COVID-19 risk. Referring to the distribution map of crustal mineral formations in Iran and comparing it with counties that have shown resistance to COVID-19 in the fourth and fifth waves, we find that the areas around the ophiolite formations (ophiolite rocks) have relative resistance to the infection-fire. These rocks contain trace metal elements (perhaps up to 10 times more than other areas [1],[2]) and therefore it can be speculated that trace metal elements and micronutrients of copper, zinc, manganese, magnesium, nickel and the like, strengthen the immune system, so it supports the body and its ability to cope with the COVID-19. This has been observed in other clinical, observational and analytical-computational studies. For example, those who used glazed enamel pots (copper, enamel, granite, cast iron, etc.) instead of Teflon for cooking had a 25 percent lower risk of COVID-19 exposure [3]. These glazes (apparently due to microscopic scratches as well as surface release of materials) release metal elements (including some heavy metals) in very low and natural concentrations during cooking, which seem to reduce COVID-19 risks. Or natural foods that contain micronutrients from metallic elements (such as zinc, copper, manganese, magnesium and natural concentrations of some other metals) reduce COVID-19 risks [4]. However, various evidences show that if the body is exposed to natural (rather than industrial) contaminations of trace metal elements (such as copper, zinc, manganese, magnesium and even natural (rather than synthetic) contaminations of some other heavy metals), Can reduce COVID-19 risks.

The above mentioned areas. The underlying map from [5]

References

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